

Thin Layer Chromatographic Studies of some Steroid Hormones using Heulandite, a Zeolite as an Adsorbent

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Using heulandite earlier, tlc separations of compounds like carbohydrates and catechol amines, carboxylic acids, amino acids and vitamins have been reported¹. In present communication we report the tlc study of some steroid hormones.

Results and Discussion

R_f values (Table 1) for steroid hormones on heulandite, silica gel G and H and for their ternary mixtures (Table 2) are given. Polarity in steroids depends markedly on the nature of the functional groups, for substituents in the 3β -positions. The polarity increase in the order : H < Cl < OCOC₆H₅ < OCH₃ < OCOCH₃ < =O < OH. Hence, the polarity of testosterone compounds shows the following decreasing order : testosterone > testosterone propionate > testosterone phenyl propionate.

TABLE 1—MIGRATION BEHAVIOUR OF STEROID HORMONES

Compd.	R_f values		
	Heulandite	Silica gel G	Silica gel H
Testosterone	0.98	0.94	0.00
Testosterone propionate	0.80	0.84	0.88
Testosterone phenyl propionate	0.72	0.94	0.79
β -Estradiol	0.89	0.86	0.88
Estradiol valerate	0.76	0.94	0.88
Estradiol benzoate	0.61	0.94	0.88
Dehydro- <i>epi</i> -androsteron	0.94	0.96	0.88
Cholesterol	0.00	0.00	0.00

If this is the case, the R_f values would have increased from testosterone to testosterone phenyl propionate. But the sequence discussed above is of limited validity, the more so because sometimes

TABLE 2—TERNARY SEPARATION OF STEROID HORMONES*

Sl. no.	Components of mixture	R_f value Heulandite
1.	8 + 6 + 7	
	Cholesterol	0.00
	Estradiol benzoate	0.58
2.	8 + 6 + 4	
	Cholesterol	0.00
	Estradiol benzoate	0.58
3.	8 + 3 + 1	
	Cholesterol	0.00
	Testosteron phenyl propionate	0.70
4.	8 + 6 + 1	
	Cholesterol	0.00
	Estradiol benzoate	0.58
5.	8 + 3 + 7	
	Cholesterol	0.00
	Testosteron phenyl propionate	0.70
	Dehydro- <i>epi</i> -androsteron	0.94

*On silica gel G and H, no separation.

inversion can occur in certain lower polar solvents used as mobile phase². The same thing happened on heulandite layer using solvent system carbon disulphide + pyridine (1:1) which has less polarity (dielectric constants of CS₂ and pyridine are 2.64, 12.40 respectively). So the adsorption behaviour is reversed, i.e. higher polar compounds showed higher migration and the lower polar ones lower migration. The same explanation is observed for estradiol compounds. Further dehydro-*epi*-androsteron

has OH group at 3β and keto group at C-17 positions, which also increase the polarity, hence higher will be the migration (0.94). In case of cholesterol which contain OH group at 3β -position should have more polarity but due to the presence of allyl group at C-17 position its polarity is reduced so the migration is retarded.

Experimental

The spot solution applied for each spot contained approximately 3.0–3.5 μg of steroid. The chromatoplates were then developed by ascending technique in a closed chamber containing solvent mixture

carbon disulphide-pyridine (1 : 1). It took 4 min for the solvent to ascend the distance of about 4–5 cm. After development, the plates were dried, cooled and kept in iodine chamber to develop colour. All the compounds showed light brown colour.

References

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